

Surfactance of Fatty Derivatives from Leather and Fish Scale Protein Hydrolysates—Utilization of Waste Protein Materials

M. M. CHAKRABARTY*, A. K. BASU, A. K. SAMANTA and A. K. GHORAI

Department of Applied Chemistry, Calcutta University

Manuscript received 31 May 1977, revised 15 March 1979, accepted 1 August 1979

Leather and Fish scale protein hydrolysates were prepared under different conditions of hydrolysis and were analysed for their amino acid compositions. Protein hydrolysates were then reacted with different fatty derivatives (e.g., fatty acids, such as lauric, oleic, etc. and their acid chlorides) at different temperatures in presence of an inert atmosphere. The reaction products were evaluated for their surfactant properties and performance characteristics with regard to their solubility, stability, lowering of surface and interfacial tensions, emulsifying power, dispersive power, relative detergency, wettability, etc. Results indicated that valuable surface active compounds could be derived from the combinations of protein hydrolysates and fatty moieties. These products were comparable to the anionics based on sulphonated derivatives in respect of their applications in hard and acidic water. These surfactants offered appreciable lowering of surface tensions and had very good detergency and wetting properties. Addition of synergists and other auxiliaries to the compositions of surfactants improved further their surface active properties, particularly in respect of relative detergency and hard water tolerance.

PREPARATION of surfactants from waste protein materials is of considerable importance from economic standpoint. Waste proteinaceous materials are abundant in our country. If organized collections are made, considerable quantities of leather scraps, fish scales, toxic seed cakes, bone, glue, horn, hoof, etc. could be utilized for the preparation of wide varieties of surfactants.

Proteins are characterised by the presence of polypeptide linkages which on hydrolysis would yield simpler amino acid moieties with peptides of different chain lengths. This amino group could be reacted with suitable acid chlorides, alkyl chlorides, fatty acids and other condensing agents to yield valuable surface active compounds.

Literature survey reveals that very little significant work has been done in the field of protein derived surfactants. First protein-derived surfactant was made in Germany during 1950's. It was an oleyl amide derivative, such as Lamepon A (German), Verapon or Maypon K which was an acid chloride condensation product made from protein derivatives of leather¹⁻³. The carboxyl group of the amino acid was reacted with an alkali to form the salt. The product was stable only to very weak acids of a pH between six and seven and was not precipitated by lime soaps. Detergency was best when assisted by an alkali such as soda ash. The lime soap dispersive power was between the alcohol sulphates and the amide-sulphonates. The product could be made also from the lower fatty acids and from stearic acid, although the latter was declared poor in foam value.

American products Maypon AL and Veripon were made from lauryl chloride, Maypon OW was the triethanolamine salt. These compounds were unusual in that they did not contain any sulphate or sulphonate group. Another group of acid chloride protein derivatives were the Medialans^{4,5}. Like the Lamepons and Maypons, they had an end carboxyl group. They were highly resistant to hard water, had about the same detergency as sodium oleate, were mild on the skin and had a softening effect on rayon and staple fibres. Their taste and odour were objectionable. Medialan A was made by condensing oleyl chloride and the sodium salt of sarcosine. The resistance to hard water of the Medialan A was very much superior to that of soap.

Very recently Sokol⁶ studied thermal condensation of fatty acids and amines with proteins, such as wool, vegetable protein, gelatin and chicken feather and suggested that useful low cost polypeptide surfactants could be prepared from protein sources.

This communication describes the results of work demonstrating the preparation of surfactants from leather scraps and fish-scales and their performance characteristics.

Experimental

Preparation of Protein Hydrolysates :

Protein hydrolysates from leather scraps and fish scales were prepared by digesting with lime at different concentrations in an autoclave at 110°

* Presented at the 29th Foundation Day Celebrations of the Indian Leather Technologists' Association on August 13, 1975.

under a pressure of 2 atmosphere by direct steam for different time intervals. Excess lime was removed by sodium carbonate treatment. Protein hydrolysates were then brought to pH 7 by adding dilute hydrochloric acid, remaining inorganic compounds were removed by dialysis and finally hydrolysates were concentrated to 60% solid content.

Preparation of Acid Chlorides :

Acid chlorides were prepared by refluxing fatty acids with thionyl chloride in 1 : 1.5 molar proportions at water bath temperature for 1 hour. Excess thionyl chloride was removed and products were distilled under vacuum.

Condensation Reaction :

Protein hydrolysates were reacted with fatty acid chlorides at 40-70° in an inert atmosphere to minimise darkening of the products and maintained at pH 8-9 by adding sodium hydroxide solution for about 4-6 hours. Different protein based surfactants were prepared by using different equivalent ratios of protein to fatty moieties. Purity of the products, i.e., their contamination with soaps was checked by thin layer chromatography and solubility data.

Methods of Analysis :

Products were tested for their detergency, surface tension, foam value, acid and alkali stability, metal ion stability, wettability characteristics and lime soap dispersive power⁷.

Results and Discussion

The surface tension, foam value, relative detergency and wetting property are shown in Tables from 1 to 4.

An examination of performance characteristics of protein derived surfactants as regards their acid and alkali stability, metal ion stability and lime soap dispersive power indicated that all these characteristics were superior to those of the soap

TABLE-1

1. Surface tension at 32°C :		
Product	Percent concentration (w/v)	Surface tension (dynes/cm)
Sodium dodecyl benzene sulphonate	0.4	25.4
Lauryl derivative of Fish scale protein hydrolysate	0.4	27.5
Lauryl derivative of leather protein hydrolysate	0.4	28.8
Distilled water	—	70.9

TABLE-2

2. Foam value and foam stability :			
Product	Percent concentration (w/v)	Initial (cm)	After 5 mins. (cm)
Sodium dodecyl benzene sulphonate	0.4	17.2	16.9
Sodium lauryl sulphate	0.4	15.3	14.2
Lauryl derivative of fish scale protein hydrolysate	0.4	14.3	13.8

TABLE-3

3. Relative Detergency :			
Product	Percent concentration (w/v)	Percent detergency	
Sodium dodecyl benzene sulphonate	0.4	67.6	
Lauryl derivative of fish scale protein hydrolysate	0.4	70.0	
Lauryl derivative of leather protein hydrolysate	0.4	63.6	

TABLE-4

4. Wettability :			
Product	Percent concentration (w/v)	Time for sinking in sec. (of standard cotton fibre)	
Sodium dodecyl benzene sulphonate	0.2	8	
Lauryl derivative of fish scale protein hydrolysate	0.2	8	
Lauryl derivative of leather protein hydrolysate	0.2	6	
Distilled water	—	10	

and comparable to the anionic based on sodium dodecyl benzene sulphonate.

Surface active compounds from leather and fish scale protein hydrolysate offered appreciable lowering of surface tensions. This fact could be utilized with advantage in different compositions for wide range of industrial applications, such as in emulsifiers, dispersing agents, penetrating agents, etc.

These surfactants had high order of detergency characteristics and could find use as cleaning agents in industrial and household applications. Lauryl derivative of fish scale protein hydrolysate was even superior in relative detergency to the anionic surfactant based on sodium dodecyl benzene sulphonate. Oleyl derivatives of protein hydrolysates were not valuable as detergents but their wetting properties were excellent. Lauryl derivative of fish scale protein hydrolysate had good foaming

characteristics. Studies were also conducted on the effects of synergists and other auxiliaries such as soaps, and results indicated, as might be anticipated, that built-in products had improved surfactant properties.

Detailed method of synthesis and performance characteristics of various protein based products will be communicated later.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by a Research Grant from University Grants Commission, New Delhi.

References

1. S. SABETY, *Oleagineux*, 1959, **14**, 179.
2. J. W. MCCUTCHEON "Synthetic Detergents", Mac Nair-Dorland Company, New York, 1950.
3. A. M. SCHWARTZ, J. W. PERRY and J. BERCH, "Surface Active Agents and Detergents, Vol. II, Interscience Publishers. Inc., New York, 1958.
4. E. JUNGERMANN, J. F. GERRECHT and I. J. KRIMS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 172.
5. W. H. ZUSSMAN and W. J. LENNON, *J. Soc. Cosmetic Chem.* 1955, **6**, 407.
6. P. E. SOKOL, *J. Amer. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 101.
7. J. C. HARRIS, "Detergency Evaluation and Testing", Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, 1954.